

Mathematical Model

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This documentation outlines the nomenclature and equations for energy system optimization models developed within the ESTRAM framework by a research group of the Leibniz University Hannover and the Institute for Solar Energy Research Hamelin (ISFH). These models are designed to determine the supply for various energy carriers to meet a given demand of different energy applications. In a typical model, capacity expansion and dispatch of energy system components are optimized to minimize system costs.

Within ESTRAM, four main categories of components are distinguished: sources, converters, storages, and consumers. Sources (e.g., solar and wind energy) supply primary energy, while storage offers temporal flexibility, converters enable the conversion of energy carriers, and consumers utilize energy carriers for specific (energy) applications.

The documentation covers a wide range of equations; however, the specific subset used depends on the particular modeling case. While we aim for generalization and comprehensiveness, it's important to note that individual models may include modifications and extensions beyond what is detailed in this documentation.

Sets

Main sets and indices

Set	Description
$c \in C$	Set of Components
$q \in Q \subset C$	Set of Sources
$x \in X \subset C$	Set of Converters
$s \in S \subset C$	Set of Storages
$u \in U \subset C$	Set of Consumers
$e \in E$	Set of Energy carriers
$a \in A$	Set of Applications
$k \in K$	Set of Nodes
$b \in B$	Set of Branches
$y \in Y$	Set of Years
$t \in T$	Set of Time steps

Subsets, index sets & other sets

Set	Description
$C^{\text{opt}} \subset C$	Optimized components
$C^{\text{fix}} \subset C$	Fixed components
$C^{\text{dep}} \subset C$	Depreciated components
$C_e^{\text{in}} \subset C$	Components with energy carrier e as input
$C_e^{\text{out}} \subset C$	Components with energy carrier e as output
Q_q^{sub}	Subclasses of source q
$X^{\text{chp}} \subset X$	Converters with combined heat and power (chp)
$X^{\text{bkp}} \subset X^{\text{chp}}$	Converters with back pressure chp
$X^{\text{ext}} \subset X^{\text{chp}}$	Converters with extraction chp
$X^{\text{non}} \subset X$	Converters without chp
$X^{\text{var}} \subset X$	Converters with variable efficiency rate
$U_a^{\text{out}} \subset C$	Consumers with application a as output
a_u	Application of consumer u
$E_c^{\text{in}} \subset E$	Input energy carriers of the component c
$B_e \subset B$	Branches of energy carrier e
$B_{\text{electricity}}^{\text{ac}} \subset B_{\text{electricity}}$	AC branches of electricity grid
$B_{\text{electricity}}^{\text{dc}} \subset B_{\text{electricity}}$	DC branches of electricity grid
$o \in O$	Set of cycles within ac electricity grid
$b \in B_o \subset B$	Set of branches within a cycle o
$g \in G \subset C$	Set of CCS plants

Parameters

General

Symbol	Unit	Description
Δt	h	Length of time steps
Δt^{ref}	h	Reference time step length - typically 1h
Δy	a	Length between optimized years

Symbol	Unit	Description
Y^{start}		Start year of the transition
Y^{end}		End year of the transition
Y^{target}		Target year of the transition
β^{wacc}		Weighted average costs of capital

Costs

Symbol	Unit	Description
$c_{e,y}^{\text{carrier}}$	EUR/MWh	Spec. fuel cost of energy carrier e in year y
$c_{e,i,y}^{\text{carrier}}$	EUR/MWh	Spec. fuel cost of energy carrier e at cost step i in year y
c_y^{CO2}	EUR/t	Spec. CO2 emission costs in year y
$c_{c,y}^{\text{var}}$	EUR/MWh	Spec. variable costs of component c in year y
$c_{c,y}^{\text{fix}}$	EUR/MW	Spec. fix costs for power capacity of component c in year y
$c_{s,y}^{\text{fix,energy}}$	EUR/MWh	Spec. fix costs for energy capacity of storage s in year y
$c_{g,y}^{\text{fix}}$	EUR/t/h	Spec. fix costs for CO2 capture capacity of CCS plant g in year y
$c_{g,y}^{\text{fix,CO2}}$	EUR/t	Spec. fix costs for CO2 storage capacity of CCS plant g in year y
$c_{c,y}^{\text{om}}$	%	O&M costs share of component c in year y
$c^{\text{sr,max}}$	EUR/km ²	Maximum space resistance against land consumption
$c_x^{\text{ramp+}}$	EUR/MW	Costs for ramping up converter x
$c_{c,y}^{\text{inst,cap}}$	%	Installation capacity costs share of component c in year y

Carriers & CO2

Symbol	Unit	Description
$\theta_k^{\text{CO2budget}}$	t	CO2 emission budget at node k
$\theta_{k,y}^{\text{CO2limit}}$	t	CO2 emission limit at node k in year y
θ_e^{CO2ef}	t/MWh	Spec. CO2 emission factor of energy carrier e
$e_{e,k,y}^{\text{import,max}}$	MWh	Max energy import of energy carrier e at node k in year y

Symbol	Unit	Description
$e_{e,k,y}^{\text{export,max}}$	MWh	Max energy export of energy carrier e at node k in year y
$p_{e,k,y}^{\text{import,max}}$	MW	Max power import of energy carrier e at node k in year y
$p_{e,k,y}^{\text{export,max}}$	MW	Max power export of energy carrier e at node k in year y
$d_{a,k,y,t}$	MW	Demand of application a at node k in year y in timestep t
$d_{a,k,y}^{\text{max}}$	MW	Maximum demand of application a at node k in year y

Stepwise imports

Symbol	Unit	Description
$i \in I$		Set of cost steps
$e_{e,i,k,y}^{\text{import,max}}$	MWh	Max energy import of energy carrier e of cost step i at node k in year y
$c_{e,i,k,y}^{\text{import,fix}}$	EUR	The y-intercept of the linear cost function of energy carrier e of cost step i at node k in year y
$c_{e,i,k,y}^{\text{import,mar}}$	EUR/MWh	The slope of the linear cost function of energy carrier e of cost step i at node k in year y

Components

Symbol	Unit	Description
λ_c	a	Life time of component c
β_c^{crf}		Capital recovery factor of component c
$p_{c,k}^{\text{max}}$	MW	(Total) capacity potential of component c at node k
$e_{s,k}^{\text{max}}$	MWh	(Total) capacity potential of storage s at node k
$\theta_{g,k}^{\text{CCS,max}}$	t	(Total) CO2 capacity potential of CCS plant g at node k
μ_c	km ² /MW	Land consumption of component c
$f_{q,k,y,t}^{\text{cap}}$		Capacity factor of source q at node k in year y in timestep t
f_x^{ramp}		Factor that represents the capability to ramp of converter x
$f_{u,k}^{\text{load}}$		Load factor of consumer u at node k

Symbol	Unit	Description
$f_{u,k,y,t}^{\text{dsm,min}}$		The capacity factor for the minimum energy in the storage of a DsmConsumer u at node k in year y in timestep t
$f_{u,k,y,t}^{\text{dsm,max}}$		The capacity factor for the maximum energy in the storage of a DsmConsumer u at node k in year y in timestep t
$\sigma_{k,x}^{\text{cb}}$		Minimum power to heat ratio of chp converter x at node k
$\sigma_{k,x}^{\text{cv}}$	MWh/MWh	Power loss coefficient of chp converter x at node k
π_s	MWh/MW	General energy to power capacity ratio of storage s
π_s^{rel}		Relative potential E2P deviation factor of separated storage s
π_u	MWh/unit of u	General energy to power capacity ratio of consumer u
$\eta_{c,k}$		Efficiency rate of component c at node k
$\eta_{c,k,y,t}$		Variable efficiency rate of component c at node k in year y in timestep t
$\eta_{x,k}^{\text{th}}$		Share of thermal output from input of chp converter x at node k
$\eta_{x,k}^{\text{fur,max}}$		Maximum fuel utilization rate of chp converter x at node k
η_s^{sd}	/h	Energy self discharge of storage s
η_s^{ch}		Efficiency rate of charging of storage s
η_s^{dis}		Efficiency rate of discharging of storage s
$\eta_{g,e,y}^{\text{CCS}}$	t/MWh	Efficiency CO2 capture rate of CCS plant g with energy carrier e in year y
$p_u^{\text{in,max}}$	MW/unit of u	The maximum power input of a DsmConsumer u
$\phi_{u,k,y}^{\text{max}}$		Maximum share of consumer u at node k in year y

Transformation

Symbol	Unit	Description
$p_{c,k,y}^{\text{exo}}$	MW	Exogenously given power capacity of component c at node k in year y
$e_{s,k,y}^{\text{exo}}$	MWh	Exogenously given energy capacity of storage s at node k in year y
$p_c^{\text{inst,cap,min}}$	MW/a	Minimum installation capacity per year of component c
$e_s^{\text{inst,cap,min}}$	MWh/a	Minimum installation capacity per year of storage s

Symbol	Unit	Description
$g_{c,y}$	%/a	Potential growth of installation capacity of component c in year y
$p_c^{\text{inst,cap,inert}}$	%/a	Inertia of power installation capacity of component c
$e_c^{\text{inst,cap,inert}}$	%/a	Inertia of energy installation capacity of component c

Grid & distribution

Symbol	Unit	Description
γ_k^{pop}		Population within the region represented by node k
γ_k^{area}	km ²	Area related to node k
$\gamma_b^{\text{distance}}$	km	Length of branch b
$l_{e,k}^{\text{grid}}$		Grid losses of energy carrier e at node k
$l_e^{\text{grid,distance}}$	/km	Grid losses per distance of energy carrier e
$p_{b,y}^{\text{nom}}$	MW	Transport capacity of branch b in year y
$\nu_{e,y}$		Grid availability of the grid of energy carrier e in year y
$\alpha_{k,b}$		1 if k is the start node of branch b
$\omega_{k,b}$		1 if k is the end node of branch b
$\kappa_{b,o}^{\text{dir}}$		Direction of branch b in cycle o
$\kappa_{k,b}^{\text{im}}$		Incidence matrix of nodes k and branches b
x_b	Ω	Reactance of branch b
$f_e^{\text{ssuf,min}}$		Minimum self-sufficiency factor for a given energy carrier e

Variables

Symbol	Unit	Description
$P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{import}}$	MW	Import of energy carrier e at node k in year y in timestep t
$P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{export}}$	MW	Export of energy carrier e at node k in year y in timestep t
$\Theta_{k,y}^{\text{CO2}}$	t	CO2 emissions at node k in year y
$P_{c,k,y}^{\text{cap}}$	MW	Power capacity of component c at node k in year y

Symbol	Unit	Description
$P_{c,k,y}^{\text{inst}}$	MW	Power capacity installation of component c at node k in year y
$P_{c,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}}$	MW	Power installation capacity of component c at node k in year y
$P_{c,k,y,t}^{\text{out}}$	MW	Power output of component c at node k in year y in timestep t
$P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out,th}}$	MW	Thermal power output of chp component x at node k in year y in timestep t
$R_{x,k,y,t}^+$	MW	Ramping up of converter x at node k in year y in timestep t
$P_{c,k,y,t}^{\text{in}}$	MW	Power input of component c at node k in year y in timestep t
$E_{s,k,y}^{\text{cap}}$	MWh	Energy capacity of storage s at node k in year y
$E_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst}}$	MWh	Energy capacity installation of storage s at node k in year y
$E_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}}$	MW	Energy installation capacity of storage s at node k in year y
$E_{s,k,y,t}$	MWh	Energy of storage s at node k in year y in timestep t
$E_{s,k,y,0}$	MWh	Initial energy of storage s at node k in year y
$T_{g,k,y}^{\text{CCS,cap}}$	t/h	CO2 capture capacity of CCS plant g at node k in year y
$T_{g,k,y}^{\text{CCS,inst}}$	t/h	CO2 capture capacity installation of CCS plant g at node k in year y
$T_{g,k,y,t}^{\text{CCS}}$	t/h	CO2 capture of CCS plant g at node k in year y in timestep t
$\Theta_{g,k,y}^{\text{CCS,cap}}$	t	CO2 storage capacity of CCS plant g at node k in year y
$\Theta_{g,k,y}^{\text{CCS,inst}}$	t	CO2 storage capacity installation of CCS plant g at node k in year y
$\Theta_{g,k,y}^{\text{CCS}}$	t	Stored CO2 of CCS plant g at node k in year y
$\Phi_{u,k,y}$		Share of consumer u at node k in year y
$P_{b,y,t}^{\text{flow}}$	MW	Power flow of b in year y in timestep t
$P_{b,y,t}^{\text{flow1}}$	MW	(+) Power flow of b in year y in timestep t
$P_{b,y,t}^{\text{flow2}}$	MW	(-) Power flow of b in year y in timestep t

Objective

The objective function minimizes energy system costs throughout the transition pathway.

$$C^{\text{total}} = \sum_y \sum_k C_{k,y}^{\text{capex}} + C_{k,y}^{\text{om}} + C_{k,y}^{\text{carrier}}$$

Component.post_read_from_model()

Calculate the costs for this component.

The total costs of the components consist of the CAPEX and costs for operation and maintenance. The CAPEX are determined by the annual power installation, the specific fixed price and the capital recovery factor of non-depreciated components. To consider also the energy of storages, a second term is needed.

$$C_{k,y}^{\text{capex}} = \sum_{z=y-\lambda_c+\Delta y}^y \sum_{c \notin C^{\text{dep}}} P_{c,k,z}^{\text{inst}} \cdot c_{c,z}^{\text{fix}} \cdot \beta_c^{\text{crf}} \\ + \sum_{z=y-\lambda_s+\Delta y}^y \sum_{s \notin C^{\text{dep}}} E_{s,k,z}^{\text{inst}} \cdot c_{s,z}^{\text{fix,energy}} \cdot \beta_s^{\text{crf}} \quad \forall k, \forall y$$

With the capital recovery factor :

$$\beta_c^{\text{crf}} = \frac{\beta^{\text{wacc}} \cdot (1 + \beta^{\text{wacc}})^{\lambda_c}}{(1 + \beta^{\text{wacc}})^{\lambda_c} - 1} \quad \forall c$$

The costs for operation and maintenance are calculated by the existing power (and energy) capacity and the share of specific O&M costs.

$$C_{k,y}^{\text{om}} = \sum_c P_{c,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \cdot c_{c,y}^{\text{om}} \cdot c_{c,y}^{\text{fix}} \\ + \sum_s E_{s,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \cdot c_{s,y}^{\text{om}} \cdot c_{s,y}^{\text{fix,energy}} \quad \forall k, \forall y$$

SingleCarrierExchange.post_read_from_model()

Calculate the costs / revenues for the carrier import / export.

The total costs of the energy carriers are calculated the following way.

$$C_{k,y}^{\text{carrier}} = \sum_e \sum_t (P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{import}} - P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{export}}) \cdot \Delta t \cdot c_{e,y}^{\text{carrier}} \quad \forall k, \forall y$$

In specific cases, other costs can be added, such as CO2 costs, ramping costs or environmental costs.

CO2.post_read_from_model()

Runs adjustments after read_from_model

Additional costs based on CO2 emissions can be added the following way.

$$C_{k,y}^{\text{CO2}} = \Theta_{k,y}^{\text{CO2}} \cdot c_y^{\text{CO2}} \quad \forall k, \forall y$$

RampingCosts.post_read_from_model()

Calculate ramping costs.

The costs for ramping up are calculated with the help of the ramp up variable and the corresponding specific costs.

$$C_{k,y}^{\text{ramp}} = \sum_x \sum_t R_{x,k,y,t}^+ \cdot c_x^{\text{ramp}+} \quad \forall k, \forall y$$

SpaceResistance.post_read_from_model()

Calculate environmental costs.

The environmental costs as a result of space resistance against land consumption.

$$C_{k,y}^{\text{env}} = \sum_q \left(\sum_{q^* \in Q_q^{\text{sub}}} P_{q^*,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{\mu_q \cdot c^{\text{sr,max}}}{2 \cdot \sum_{q^* \in Q_q^{\text{sub}}} P_{q^*,k,y}^{\text{max}}} \quad \forall k, \forall y$$

InstallationCapacity.post_read_from_model()

Calculate ramping costs.

If a modeling approach for the installation capacity is chosen, there exist also installation capacity costs. Those are derived by the fix costs of a component and a contingency share for the installation capacity.

$$C_{k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} = \sum_c P_{c,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \cdot c_{c,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \cdot c_{c,y}^{\text{fix}} + \sum_s E_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \cdot c_{s,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \cdot c_{s,y}^{\text{fix,energy}} \quad \forall k, \forall y$$

Further costs may be added in near future.

Constraints

CO2

There are two options of limiting CO2 emissions: annual limits or an overall budget. Both options aggregate emissions and their limits over all considered regions as the default.

CO2Path.build_emissions_max_constr(model, emission_var)

The annual CO2 limitation is computed accordingly. It may also be specified that the CO2 limit must be met at any node individually.

$$\sum_k \Theta_{k,y}^{\text{CO2}} \leq \sum_k \theta_{k,y}^{\text{CO2limit}} \quad \forall y$$

Parameters

model (estram.model.Model) –

emission_var (estram.model.Var) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

CO2Budget.build_emissions_max_constr(*model, emission_var*)

The budget consists out of two constraints. The first is related to all accounted CO2 emissions weighted with the year step width. The first year is only weighted with $(\text{step_width} + 1) / 2$ to account for the fact that it is at the border of the simulation. The last year is 0 anyways and doesn't need a weight.

$$\sum_k \Theta_{k, Y^{\text{start}}}^{\text{CO2}} \cdot \frac{\Delta y + 1}{2} + \sum_{y=Y^{\text{start}}+\Delta y}^{Y^{\text{end}}} \Theta_{k,y}^{\text{CO2}} \cdot \Delta y \leq \sum_k \theta_k^{\text{CO2budget}}$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) -

emission_var (*estram.model.Var*) -

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

CO2Budget.build_emissions_end_constr(*model, emission_var*)

This constrained assures zero energetic CO2 emissions from a given target year onwards and to reach the budget in a final and sustainable way.

$$\Theta_{k,y}^{\text{CO2}} = 0 \quad \forall k, \forall y \geq Y^{\text{target}}$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) -

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

CO2.build_balance_expression(*import_vars*)

Annual CO2 emissions are calculated by accounting all energy carriers with their related CO2 emission factor within a year.

$$\Theta_{k,y}^{\text{CO2}} = \sum_e \sum_t P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{import}} \cdot \Delta t \cdot \theta_e^{\text{CO2ef}} \quad \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

import_vars (*dict*) - key: carrier name value: *estram.model.Var*

Depending on the investigated scenario, the additional option of carbon, capture and storage technologies may be considered.

CCS.modify_emissions_constr(*capture_var*)

If CCS is considered, the annual CO2 emissions are reduced by the CO2 capture of CCS plants.

$$\Theta_{k,y}^{\text{CO2}} = \sum_e \sum_t P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{import}} \cdot \Delta t \cdot \theta_e^{\text{CO2ef}} - \sum_g \sum_t T_{g,k,y,t}^{\text{CCS}} \cdot \Delta t \quad \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

import_vars (*dict*) – key: carrier name value: `estram.model.Var`

CCS.build_capture_var(*model*)

To capture CO2 from the ambient air, energy needs to be supplied. Depending on the technology used, more than one energy carrier must be provided and also accounted for in the energy balance.

$$P_{g,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} \cdot \eta_{g,e,y}^{\text{CCS}} = T_{g,k,y,t}^{\text{CCS}} \quad \forall g, \forall e, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (`estram.model.Model`) –

Returns

var

Return type

`estram.model.Var`

CCS.build_max_capture_constr(*model, inst_capture_cap_var, capture_var*)

CO2 capturing must not exceed the installed capture capacity of CCS plant.

$$T_{g,k,y,t}^{\text{CCS}} \leq T_{g,k,y}^{\text{CCS,cap}} \quad \forall g, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (`estram.model.Model`) –

inst_cap_var (`estram.model.Var`) –

stored_co2_var (`estram.model.Var`) –

Returns

Return type

`estram.model.Constraint`

CCS.build_storage_constr(*model, stored_co2_var, capture_var*)

Stored CO2 in CCS is derived by previous stored CO2 and input processes considering length of timesteps and years.

$$\Theta_{g,k,y}^{\text{CCS}} = \Theta_{g,k,y-\Delta y}^{\text{CCS}} + \Delta y \cdot \sum_t T_{g,k,y,t}^{\text{CCS}} \cdot \Delta t \quad \forall g, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

- model** (*estram.model.Model*) –
- stored_co2_var** (*estram.model.Var*) –
- capture_var** (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

CCS.build_max_stored_co2_constr(*model, inst_cap_var, stored_co2_var*)

CO2 content in a storage must not exceed the installed storage capacity of a CCS plant.

$$\Theta_{g,k,y}^{\text{CCS}} \leq \Theta_{g,k,y}^{\text{CCS,cap}} \quad \forall g, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

- model** (*estram.model.Model*) –
- inst_cap_var** (*estram.model.Var*) –
- stored_co2_var** (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

CCS.build_stored_co2_var(*model*)

Capacity of CCS cannot exceed the given potential.

$$\Theta_{g,k,y}^{\text{CCS,cap}} \leq \theta_{g,k}^{\text{CCS,max}} \quad \forall g, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

- model** (*estram.model.Model*) –

Returns

var

Return type

estram.model.Var

CAPEX and O&M costs as well as dimensioning and installation for CCS plants are considered the same way as for energy storages.

Energy balance

Scenario.build_model()

Build a mathematical model of the system.

The system balance consisting of energy carrier supply and demand must always be met at any time and node. Transmission losses are accounted for on the supply side of the flow variable and depend on the distance. Distribution losses are considered only before the end use by consumers.

$$\begin{aligned}
& P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{import}} + \sum_{q,x,s \in C_e^{\text{out}}} P_{c,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} \\
& + \sum_{b \in B_e} (P_{b,y,t}^{\text{flow1}} \cdot \omega_{k,b} - P_{b,y,t}^{\text{flow2}} \cdot \alpha_{k,b}) \cdot (1 - \gamma_b^{\text{distance}} \cdot l_e^{\text{grid,distance}}) \\
& = P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{export}} + \sum_{x,s,g \in C_e^{\text{in}}} P_{c,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} + \sum_{u \in C_e^{\text{in}}} P_{u,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} \cdot \frac{1}{1 - l_{e,k}^{\text{grid}}} \\
& + \sum_{b \in B_e} (P_{b,y,t}^{\text{flow1}} \cdot \alpha_{k,b} - P_{b,y,t}^{\text{flow2}} \cdot \omega_{k,b}) \quad \forall e, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t
\end{aligned}$$

Returns

model

Return type

estram.model.Model

Operation

`Source.build_power_constr(model, inst_cap_var, power_var)`

Operation of sources does not exceed their capacities for every timestep

$$P_{q,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} \leq P_{q,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \cdot f_{q,k,y,t}^{\text{cap}} \quad \forall q, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

`model` (*estram.model.Model*) –

`inst_cap_var` (*estram.model.Var*) –

`power_var` (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

`Converter.build_power_constr(model, model_input, power_out_var)`

Power output of non chp converters is linked to its power input and its efficiency rate. Variable converters have a time-dependent efficiency. Converters may have a dual input.

$$P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} = \sum_{e \in E_x^{\text{in}}} P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} \cdot \eta_{x,k,y,t} \quad \forall x \notin X^{\text{ext}}, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

model_input (*estram.model.Var*) –

power_out_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

Converter.build_power_max_constr(*model, power_out_var, inst_cap_var*)

Operation of converters does not exceed their capacities for every timestep.

$$P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} \leq P_{x,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \quad \forall x, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

power_out_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

inst_cap_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

BkpConverter.build_power2_constr(*model, power_in_var, power_out2_var*)

The thermal power output of backpressure chp converters is linked to its power input and its thermal efficiency rate.

$$P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out,th}} = P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} \cdot \eta_{x,k}^{\text{th}} \quad \forall x \in X^{\text{bcp}}, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

power_in_var (*estram.Model.Var*) –

power_out2_var (*estram.Model.Var*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

ExtConverter.build_power_ext_constr(*model, power_in_var, power_out_var, power_out2_var*)

The power input of extraction chp converters can be calculated with primary and secondary

(thermal) power output, power loss factor and efficiency rate.

$$P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} + P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out,th}} \cdot \sigma_{k,x}^{\text{cv}} = P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} \cdot \eta_{x,k} \quad \forall x \in X^{\text{ext}}, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

- `model` (*estram.model.Model*) –
- `power_in_var` (*estram.Model.Var*) –
- `power_out_var` (*estram.Model.Var*) –
- `power_out2_var` (*estram.Model.Var*) –

Returns

- `constr`

Return type

- `estram.model.Constraint`

`ExtConverter.build_power_min_constr(model, power_out_var, power_out2_var)`

For extraction chp converters, a minimum power to heat ratio needs to be considered.

$$P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} \geq P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out,th}} \cdot \sigma_{k,x}^{\text{cb}} \quad \forall x \in X^{\text{ext}}, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

- `model` (*estram.model.Model*) –
- `power_out_var` (*estram.Model.Var*) –
- `power_out2_var` (*estram.Model.Var*) –

Returns

- `constr`

Return type

- `estram.model.Constraint`

`ExtConverter.build_power_max_ext_constr(model, power_out_var, power_out2_var, inst_cap_var)`

Maximum primary power output of extraction chp converters depends on secondary power output and power loss factor and cannot exceed its capacity.

$$P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} + P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out,th}} \cdot \sigma_{k,x}^{\text{cv}} \leq P_{x,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \quad \forall x \in X^{\text{ext}}, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

- `model` (*estram.model.Model*) –
- `power_out_var` (*estram.Model.Var*) –
- `power_out2_var` (*estram.Model.Var*) –
- `inst_cap_var` (*estram.Model.Var*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

ChpConverter.build_fur_max_constr(*model*, *model_input*, *power_out_var*, *power_out2_var*)

Total power outputs of chp converters physically cannot exceed the (fuel) input power.

$$P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} + P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out,th}} \leq P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} \cdot \eta_{x,k}^{\text{fur,max}} \quad \forall x \in X^{\text{chp}}, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

model_input (*estram.model.Var*) –

power_out_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

power_out2_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

Storage.build_power_max_constr(*model*, *inst_power_var*, *power_var*, *direction*)

Power input of storages is limited by power capacity.

$$P_{s,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} \leq P_{s,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \quad \forall s, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Power output of storages is limited by power capacity.

$$P_{s,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} \leq P_{s,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \quad \forall s, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

inst_power_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

power_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

direction (*str*) – Suffix for the direction of powerflow. Should be 'in' or 'out'.

Returns

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

Storage.build_storage_model_constr(*model*, *energy_var*, *power_in_var*, *power_out_var*)

Energy content in storage is derived by previous energy content, self discharge and input and

output processes including efficiency losses.

$$E_{s,k,y,t} = E_{s,k,y,t-\Delta t} \cdot (1 - \eta^{\text{sd}} \cdot \Delta t^{\text{ref}})^{\Delta t / \Delta t^{\text{ref}}} + \Delta t \cdot (P_{s,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} \cdot \eta_s^{\text{ch}} - P_{s,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_s^{\text{dis}}}) \quad \forall s, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

To account for correct self-discharge with long time steps length, an exponentiation formulation is chosen that can be derived from building a series with smaller time steps, referred as the reference time step length.

Parameters

- model** (*estram.model.Model*) –
- energy_var** (*estram.model.Var*) –
- power_in_var** (*estram.model.Var*) –
- power_out_var** (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

Storage.build_energy_max_constr(*model, inst_energy_var, energy_var*)

Energy content of storages cannot exceed energy storage capacity.

$$E_{s,k,y,t} \leq E_{s,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \quad \forall s, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

- model** (*estram.model.Model*) –
- inst_energy_var** (*estram.model.Var*) –
- energy_var** (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

Consumer.build_power_constr(*model, model_input, power_out_var*)

The output of consumers is derived by its power input and a variable efficiency rate.

$$P_{u,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} = P_{u,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} \cdot \eta_{u,k,y,t} \quad \forall u, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

- model** (*estram.model.Model*) –
- model_input** (*estram.model.Var*) –
- power_out_var** (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

Consumer.build_share_var(*model*)

Build variable representing the consumer's share of the app. The output of a consumer is the demand times its share.

$$P_{u,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} = \Phi_{u,k,y} \cdot \sum_{a \in A_u} d_{a,k,y,t}$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

Returns

var

Return type

estram.model.Var

Some physical applications, such as hot water and space heating are provided by a single consumer. They are therefore combined in the model. This means that *a* might refer to a summation of physical applications.

Consumer.build_inst_cap_constr(*model, inst_cap_var, share_var*)

Consumer split the supply of an application based on their effective capacity compared to the total demand into shares.

$$f_{u,k}^{\text{load}} \cdot P_{u,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \geq \Phi_{u,k,y} \cdot d_{a_u,k,y}^{\text{max}} \quad \forall u, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

inst_cap_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

share_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

ConsumerContainer.build_app_coverage_constr(*model*)

Total consumer capacity for an application needs to cover the maximum application demand.

$$\sum_{u \in U_a^{\text{out}}} \Phi_{u,k,y} = 1 \quad \forall a, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

DsmConsumer.build_power_in_max_constr(*model, power_in_vars, inst_cap*)

Maximum power to charge the DSM buffer storage with

$$P_{u,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} \frac{1}{\eta_u^{\text{ch}}} \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_u} \leq P_{u,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \cdot p_u^{\text{in,max}} \quad \forall u, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

power_in_vars (*Dict[str, estram.model.Var]*) –

inst_cap (*estram.model.Var* or *estram.model.Coefficient*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

DsmConsumer.build_storage_model_constr(*model, energy_var, model_input, power_out*)

Energy content in storage is derived by previous energy content and input and output processes including efficiency losses.

$$E_{u,k,y,t} = E_{u,k,y,t-\Delta t} + \Delta t \cdot \left(P_{u,k,y,t}^{\text{in}} \cdot \eta_u^{\text{ch}} \cdot \eta_u - P_{u,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_u^{\text{dis}}} \right) \quad \forall u, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

energy_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

model_input (*estram.model.Var*) –

power_out (*estram.model.Var* or *estram.model.Coefficient*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

DsmConsumer.build_cap_min_constr(model, energy_var, inst_cap)

Energy stored in storage must not fall below the minimum capacity required.

$$E_{u,k,y,t} \geq P_{u,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \cdot f_{u,k,y,t}^{\text{dsm,min}} \cdot \pi_u \quad \forall u, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

energy_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

inst_cap (*estram.model.Var* or *estram.model.Coefficient*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

DsmConsumer.build_cap_max_constr(model, energy_var, inst_cap)

Energy stored in storage must not rise above the maximum capacity possible.

$$E_{u,k,y,t} \leq P_{u,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \cdot f_{u,k,y,t}^{\text{dsm,max}} \cdot \pi_u \quad \forall u, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

energy_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

inst_cap (*estram.model.Var* or *estram.model.Coefficient*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

SingleCarrierExchange.build_import_var(model)

Build import variable.

The variable is bound by the import limit if available.

$$P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{import}} \leq p_{e,k,y}^{\text{import,max}} \quad \forall e, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

Returns

var

Return type

estram.model.Var

SingleCarrierExchange.build_export_var(model)

Build export variable.

The variable is bound by the export limit if available.

$$P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{export}} \leq p_{e,k,y}^{\text{export,max}} \quad \forall e, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (estram.model.Model) -

Returns

var

Return type

estram.model.Var

SingleCarrierExchange.build_import_energy_constr(model, import_var)

Build constraint to limit import energy.

$$\sum_t P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{import}} \cdot \Delta t \leq e_{e,k,y}^{\text{import,max}} \quad \forall e, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (estram.model.Model) -

import_var (estram.model.Var) -

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

SingleCarrierExchange.build_export_energy_constr(model, export_var)

Build constraint to limit export energy.

$$\sum_t P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{export}} \cdot \Delta t \leq e_{e,k,y}^{\text{export,max}} \quad \forall e, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (estram.model.Model) -

export_var (estram.model.Var) -

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

ConstantImportExport.build_const_constr(*model, var, direction*)

To avoid unrealistic high flexibility supply by imports, the power import of an energy carrier e_0 can be constrained to be constant throughout the year.

$$P_{e_0,k,y,t}^{\text{import}} = P_{e_0,k,y,t-\Delta t}^{\text{import}} \quad \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters**model** (*estram.model.Model*) -**var** (*estram.model.Var*) -**direction** (*str*) -**Returns****constr****Return type**

estram.model.Constraint

A more nuanced import potential of energy carriers can be applied, which allows to set heterogeneously priced import volumes.

StepwiseCarrierImport.build_import_var(*model*)

Build import variable, which is the summed import over all cost steps.

The variable is bound by the import limit.

$$P_{e,k,y,t}^{\text{import}} \leq \sum_i c_{e,i,k,y}^{\text{import,max}} \quad \forall e, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters**model** (*estram.model.Model*) -**Returns****var****Return type**

estram.model.Var

StepwiseCarrierImport.build_obj_proxy_import_constr(*model, obj_proxy_var, import_var, intercept, slope, cost_step*)

Build the constraint for the *obj_proxy_var*, which builds the solution space of the total import costs with increasing specific costs for an increasing amount.

$$C_{e,k,y}^{\text{carrier}} \geq c_{e,i,k,y}^{\text{import,fix}} + c_{e,i,y}^{\text{carrier}} \cdot c_{e,i,k,y}^{\text{import,max}} \quad \forall e, \forall i, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

obj_proxy_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

import_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

intercept (*pd.Series*) –

slope (*pd.Series*) –

cost_step (*int*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

Grid.build_power_max_constr(*model, inst_cap_var, power_flow_var, direction*)

Power flow cannot exceed installed transport capacity adjusted by the grid availability.

$$P_{b,y,t}^{\text{flow1}} \leq P_{b,y}^{\text{cap}} \cdot \nu_{e,y} \quad \forall b \in B_e, \forall e, \forall y, \forall t$$

$$P_{b,y,t}^{\text{flow2}} \leq P_{b,y}^{\text{cap}} \cdot \nu_{e,y} \quad \forall b \in B_e, \forall e, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model –

inst_cap_var –

power_flow_var –

direction –

GridElectricity.build_voltage_law_constr(*model, power_flow_var1, power_flow_var2, cycle_df*)

Builds the Kirchhof voltage law, in case linear optimal power flow is selected. Besides the power flows, the orientation and reactance of the branches need to be considered in any cycle.

$$\sum_{b \in B_o} (P_{b,y,t}^{\text{flow1}} - P_{b,y,t}^{\text{flow2}}) \cdot \kappa_{b,o}^{\text{dir}} \cdot x_b = 0 \quad \forall o, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

power_flow_var1 (*estram.model.Var*) –

power_flow_var2 (*estram.model.Var*) –

cycle_df (*pd.DataFrame*) – index: cycles columns: self.ac_branches

Returns

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

Transformation

`Component.build_inst_cap_var(model, bind=<object object>, cap_type='power', potential=<object object>)`

Build a variable for an installed capacity..

$$P_{c,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \leq p_{c,k}^{\text{max}} \quad \forall c, \forall k, \forall y$$

$$E_{s,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \leq e_{s,k}^{\text{max}} \quad \forall s, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

bind (*pandas.Series*) – Which Series to bind the variable to.

cap_type (*str, optional*) – Which type of capacity this variable represents. Must match a column in *self.fix_costs*. Default is 'power'.

potential (*pd.Series, optional*) – Potential (per node) for the installed

Returns

Return type

estram.model.Var

Notes

The *build_dimensioning_constr* and 'build_obj_proxy_constr' methods expect the output of this method as the *inst_cap_var* argument. This is important when *self.future == 'fixed'*: Then, the methods expect to get a Coefficient as the *inst_cap_var* argument, whose *value* attribute points to the respective installed capacity series. The series might be modified by the methods. If you edit the Coefficient, ensure that its *value* attribute is the installed capacity series itself and NOT a copy of it.

`Component.build_dimensioning_constr(model, inst_cap_var, comm_var, name_suf=")`

Capacity of components is determined by installation and lifetime if transition inertia is selected. In overnight scenarios component capacity is equal to the annual installation.

$$P_{c,k,y}^{\text{cap}} = \sum_{z=y-\lambda_c+\Delta y}^y P_{c,k,z}^{\text{inst}} \quad \forall c, \forall k, \forall y$$

$$E_{s,k,y}^{\text{cap}} = \sum_{z=y-\lambda_s+\Delta y}^y E_{s,k,z}^{\text{inst}} \quad \forall s, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

inst_cap_var (*estram.model.Var* or *estram.model.Coefficient*) –

comm_var (*estram.model.Var* or *estram.model.Coefficient*) –

name_suf (*str*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint or None

Component.build_comm_var(*model*, *bind*=<object object>, *comm_type*='power', *potential*=<object object>)

As a default, the capacity of components can be increased freely by new installations. However, there are two alternative modeling options that take into account other circumstances. First, for fixed components, the installed capacity can be fixed, which allows to meet exogenously given targets or just the preservation of an existing installed capacity. Then, the corresponding installation is determined accordingly. Second, components can be depreciated, which considers existing technologies that are not longer being built but may be decommissioned when they are not used anymore. In over night scenarios, such technologies cannot be used at all.

$$P_{c,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \leq P_{c,k,y-\Delta y}^{\text{cap}} \quad \forall c \in C^{\text{dep}}, \forall k, \forall y$$
$$E_{s,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \leq E_{s,k,y-\Delta y}^{\text{cap}} \quad \forall s \in C^{\text{dep}}, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

bind (*pandas.Series*) – Which Series to bind the variable to.

comm_type (*str*, *optional*) – Which type of commissioning this variable represents. Default is 'power'.

potential (*bool*, *optional*) – If False, do not set the potential according to *component.capacity_potential* as upper limit. This is for the consumers and power vars of the storages, which need a different potential. Default is True.

Returns

var – The commissioning variable

Return type

estram.model.Var or estram.model.Coefficient

Notes

The *build_dimensioning_constr* and 'build_obj_proxy_constr' methods expect the output of this method as the *comm_var* argument. This is important when *self.future* == 'fixed': Then, the methods expect to get a Coefficient as the *comm_var* argument, whose *value* attribute points to the respective commissioning series. The series might be modified by the methods. If you edit the Coefficient, ensure that its *value* attribute is the commissioning series itself and NOT a copy of it.

Component.build_comm_limits_constr(*model*, *comm_var*)

In transition scenarios, installation of components is limited based on growth of existing installation capacity from previous period and a general minimum installation capacity if no

other model approach is selected.

The general formulation is followed by the storage capacity and the specific case of subtypes of a source.

$$\sum_k P_{c,k,y}^{\text{inst}} \leq \sum_k P_{c,k,y-\Delta y}^{\text{inst}} \cdot (1 + g_{c,y})^{\Delta y} + p_c^{\text{inst,cap,min}} \cdot \Delta y \quad \forall c, \forall y$$

$$\sum_k E_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst}} \leq \sum_k E_{s,k,y-\Delta y}^{\text{inst}} \cdot (1 + g_{s,y})^{\Delta y} + e_s^{\text{inst,cap,min}} \cdot \Delta y \quad \forall s, \forall y$$

$$\sum_k \sum_{q \in Q_q^{\text{sub}}} P_{q,k,y}^{\text{inst}} \leq \sum_k \left(\sum_{q^* \in Q_q^{\text{sub}}} P_{q^*,k,y-\Delta y}^{\text{inst}} \right) \cdot (1 + g_{q,y})^{\Delta y} + p_q^{\text{inst,cap,min}} \cdot \Delta y \quad \forall q, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

comm_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

Storage.build_e2p_max_constr(*model, inst_cap_var, inst_power_cap_var*)

New storage installations can vary inside a given range around the power to energy capacity ratio. This is the upper bound.

$$E_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst}} \leq P_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst}} \cdot \pi_s \cdot \pi_s^{\text{rel}} \quad \forall s, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

inst_cap_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

inst_power_cap_var (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

Storage.build_e2p_min_constr(*model, inst_energy_var, inst_power_var*)

New storage installations can vary inside a given range around the power to energy capacity ratio. This is the lower bound.

$$E_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst}} \geq P_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst}} \cdot \pi_s \cdot \frac{1}{\pi_s^{\text{rel}}} \quad \forall s, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

`inst_energy_var` (*estram.model.Var*) –

`inst_power_var` (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

Return type

`estram.model.Constraint`

Plug-ins

Depending on desired scenarios, it is possible to add plugins to the core model. In the following, some common plugins are described.

RampingCosts.build_ramp_up_constr(*model, power_out_var, ramp_up_var*)

The ramp up of a converter is computed the following way.

$$R_{x,k,y,t}^+ \geq P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} - P_{x,k,y,t-\Delta t}^{\text{out}} \quad \forall x, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

`model` (*estram.model.Model*) –

`power_out_var` (*estram.model.Var*) –

`ramp_up_var` (*estram.model.Var*) –

Returns

`constr`

Return type

`estram.model.Constraint`

Ramping.build_ramp_constr(*model, power_out_var, inst_cap_var, direction*)

Ramping up and down converters from one timestep to the next one is limited by the ramping factor the following way.

$$P_{x,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \cdot f_x^{\text{ramp}} \cdot \Delta t \geq P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} - P_{x,k,y,t-\Delta t}^{\text{out}} \quad \forall x, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

$$P_{x,k,y}^{\text{cap}} \cdot f_x^{\text{ramp}} \cdot \Delta t \geq P_{x,k,y,t-\Delta t}^{\text{out}} - P_{x,k,y,t}^{\text{out}} \quad \forall x, \forall k, \forall y, \forall t$$

Parameters

`model` (*estram.model.Model*) –

`power_out_var` (*estram.model.Var*) –

`inst_cap_var` (*estram.model.Var*) –

`direction` (*str*) –

Returns

`constr`

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

ExoPath.build_exo_path_constr(*model, nodes, var, path_type, factor=1*)

Builds an exogenous constraint for the installed capacity of a component. The constraints can require a component's installed capacity to reach a minimum, maximum or an exact value.

$$P_{c,k,y}^{\text{cap}} = p_{c,k,y}^{\text{exo}} \quad \forall c \in C^{\text{extrmfix}}, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

nodes (*list*) – Nodes for which a common constraint is created.

var (*estram.model.Var*) – Dimensioning var to be constrained.

path_type (*{'min', 'equal', 'max'}*) – Type of the constraint to be created.

factor (*float, optional*) – The exo paths values are multiplied by this. Needed for the HintedExoPath.

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

InstallationCapacity.build_installation_cap_var(*model, comp, bind=None, cost_type=None, set_potential=True*)

Installation capacity of components cannot exceed either the given total potential or a given maximum installation capacity.

$$P_{c,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \leq p_{c,k}^{\text{inst,cap,max}} \quad \forall c, \forall k, \forall y$$

$$E_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \leq e_{s,k}^{\text{inst,cap,max}} \quad \forall s, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

bind (*pandas.Series*) – Which Series to bind the variable to.

comp (*estram.Component*) –

cost_type (*str, optional*) – Which cost type to use. Must match column in *self.component.fix_costs*. Default is *self.component.primary_unit*.

set_potential (*bool, optional*) – If False, do not set the potential according to *component.capacity_potential* as upper limit. This is for the consumers and power vars of the storages, which need a different potential. Default is True.

Returns**Return type**

InstallationCapacity.build_installation_limits_constr(*model*, *comp*)

The scenario provides an installation capacity variable, that serves as an upper bound for the installation.

$$\sum_k P_{c,k,y}^{\text{inst}} \leq \sum_k P_{c,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \quad \forall c, \forall y$$

$$\sum_k E_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst}} \leq \sum_k E_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \quad \forall s, \forall y$$

For sources with subtypes the installation limits are aggregated as the same technologies are being produced and installed. Therefore, all constraints that affect the installation capacity need to be adjusted.

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

comp (*estram.Component*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

InstallationCapacity.build_installation_cap_max_constr(*model*, *comp*)

The maximum growth of installation capacity is limited by a growth factor and an always available minimum installation capacity.

$$\sum_k P_{c,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \leq \sum_k P_{c,k,y-\Delta y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \cdot (1 + g_{c,y})^{\Delta y} + p_c^{\text{inst,cap,min}} \cdot \Delta y \quad \forall c, \forall y$$

$$\sum_k E_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \leq \sum_k E_{s,k,y-\Delta y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \cdot (1 + g_{s,y})^{\Delta y} + e_s^{\text{inst,cap,min}} \cdot \Delta y \quad \forall s, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) –

comp (*estram.Component*) –

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

InstallationCapacity.build_installation_cap_min_constr(*model*, *comp*)

If a scenario with a variable for the installation capacity is chosen, the inertia of the installation capacity is considered. The lower bound is determined by an inertia parameter.

$$P_{c,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \geq P_{c,k,y-\Delta y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \cdot (p_c^{\text{inst,cap,inert}})^{\Delta y} \quad \forall c, \forall k, \forall y$$

$$E_{s,k,y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \geq E_{s,k,y-\Delta y}^{\text{inst,cap}} \cdot (e_s^{\text{inst,cap,inert}})^{\Delta y} \quad \forall s, \forall k, \forall y$$

Parameters

model (*estram.model.Model*) -

comp (*estram.Component*) -

Returns

constr

Return type

estram.model.Constraint

Other plugins comprise endogenous technological learning, self-sufficient energy supply, equality considerations or load shedding. More will follow in the future.